

Didactic Unit

An educational program for schoolchildren (10–13-year-old) through the use of a video game expressly developed to address and raise awareness about the problem of marine litter, to increase ocean literacy and encourage conservation-attitudes towards ocean protection

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Video games
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1 Introduction

This activity presents an educational program for school pupils (10–13-year-old) in Croatia, Italy, Malta, Portugal and Spain through the use of a video game expressly developed to address and raise awareness about the problem of marine litter and ghost gear. This didactic unit is intended to be used as support material for teachers and educational managers. It is accompanied by a set of three educational video games that encourage pupils to learn information in a fun but realistic way about some of the sources and types of litter derived from land, impacts of ghost gear and associated problems for the oceans. The approach is participative, cooperative and practical. The groups of pupils, guided by their teacher, will be able to understand the importance of conservation of the ocean in a fun and entertaining way. The materials are available in Croatian, Italian, Maltese, Portuguese, Spanish and English and can be freely downloaded from the NETTAG+ website (<https://nettagplus.eu/resources/>).

2 Objectives

This activity involves a set of three video games that can be played on a computer in the classroom or other device such as tablets. The games present several challenges relating to marine litter and ghost gear which players can discuss with each other and tackle individually or collectively in the games: cleaning up litter from beaches to prevent it from reaching the oceans; retrieving floating nets and marine litter to prevent animals from being trapped; and collecting ghost gear from fishing vessels sinking into the seafloor. By enabling students to experience these problems through experimental scenarios and by taking on the role of different stakeholders (e.g. divers and citizens), we also intend to stimulate individual thinking as well as group discussion and debate about potential solutions to resolve and prevent these problems.

Each game has a different storyline and objective. The games involve different levels of difficulty so players can progress from the lowest level to the highest as they learn how to play and develop skills and knowledge. Pupils are organised into teams (ideally of 3 to 4 players) and take turns to complete the three games.

Mission 1: Beach Clean-up

Players control a character on a beach and must plan a sequence of movements in advance to collect litter efficiently. The beach begins relatively quiet, but as the mission progresses, more people arrive, increasing the challenge. Players must distinguish between trash and marine organisms while navigating around beachgoers, such as tourists, without disturbing them. Through this mission, players learn how small local actions can contribute to a broader environmental impact.

Figure 1: Screenshot of Mission 1, Beach Clean-up

Mission 2 Rescue Route

Floating litter and lost fishing gear are trapping sea animals like sharks, dolphins, and turtles. Players must move the trash and guide the animals to safety, clearing a path for them to escape. This mission shows how floating litter in the ocean and lost fishing gear can affect marine life.

Figure 2: Screenshot of Mission 2, Rescue Route.

Game 3 Net Retrievers

This game aims to address the problem of lost or abandoned fishing gear that harms the ocean and seafloor. Players help a diver reach these nets and retrieve them from the sea. The game also introduces another tool used to recover fishing gear: tracking tags. These tags send a signal to fishers, showing the location of the nets so they can retrieve them themselves.

Figure 3: Screenshot of Mission 3, Net Retrievers.

3 Participants

The activity is aimed at school children in primary education aged 10-13 years old. It consists of an educational session guided by their teachers with a duration of 1.5 hours with each class.

4 Focus

The focus of this activity is predominantly participatory, cooperative and practical. The group of pupils can achieve the desired objectives in a fun and entertaining way.

5 Context

Every year, around 11 million metric tons of plastic reach the ocean that should have gone to landfill or another waste management centre but end up in the ocean instead. This is equivalent to a garbage truck of plastics entering the ocean each minute. This marine litter is transported to the coast and eventually to the sea by the wind, rain, sewage and rivers. Another source of ocean plastic pollution is from fishing gear which has been abandoned, discarded or lost at sea (also known as “ghost gear” because they are largely made of plastics and once lost at sea they can float around the oceans for years unintentionally trapping and injuring or killing marine life).

It is estimated that ghost gear makes up about 50% to 70% of all floating macroplastics (plastics over 5mm in size). An additional smaller amount of marine litter comes from maritime activities, for example litter thrown overboard from sea vessels.

Because marine litter comes in all shapes and sizes, it affects both shallow and deep parts of the ocean. Some of it floats on the water surface and is carried by sea currents; some can remain suspended in the water column while heavier items can sink and settle on the seafloor. The presence of this type of pollution in the ocean has serious consequences for marine life. Plastic waste and marine litter can be mistaken for food and ingested by various animals, from the smallest (e.g. seahorses, shrimps and fish) to the largest (e.g. sharks, dolphins, whales and seabirds that hunt for fish), thus entering the marine food chain and potentially reaching humans when we consume seafood. Furthermore, plastics can form into tangles of waste that trap or injure animals. Because a large part of this waste ends up on the seafloor, it can also cause damage and destruction to marine habitats. Some of the litter returns to land on the tides and accumulates on beaches and coastal areas, so litter contaminates all parts of the marine environment (oceans, beaches and coastlines).

For humans to be able to reduce the amount of marine litter that pollutes the ocean, we all need to change our behaviour. For example, we need to minimise the use of single-use plastics (like plastic bottles, take-away containers, cups and straws), regularly clean up beaches and coastlines to remove litter and ghost gear, and commit to waste recycling all over the world.

6 Requirements to play

- The game medium can be played on any device with internet access that is able to open the NETTAG+ website, but ideally on Windows personal computers (PC) or tablets.
- Video game (downloaded from: <https://nettagplus.eu/resources/>)
- Once the game has been launched, players can choose from the available languages (Croatian, English, Italian, Maltese, Portuguese and Spanish).
- 1 copy of the experience record for each pupil

7 Procedure

Begin by reading the introductory information presented in the section 'Context'. This can be used as an exercise in learning new vocabulary and ideas.

Organise pupils into teams (ideally of 3 to 4 players).

Play the three games. Throughout the games, players can experience different perspectives by playing different roles, such as citizens collecting litter on the beach (Mission 1); rescuers clearing a path for marine animals trapped by dangerous nets and marine litter (Mission 2); and divers retrieving lost nets from the seafloor or using tracking tags to help return nets to fishing boats (Mission 3).

Before moving on to the experience record, discuss the games with pupils to ask what they thought about the different challenges they had to tackle, and the roles they played. Discuss what the games represent and what are the consequences of marine litter to marine life and habitats, the marine environment (oceans, beaches and coastlines), and humans.

To conclude the activity, ask pupils to individually answer the questions in the experience record. Then use the questions to stimulate discussion and debate with the whole group about real life problems regarding marine litter, and to collectively identify possible solutions to reduce and prevent litter from entering the marine environment.

8 Experience record: Show what you've learned!

1. Describe the objective of playing the three video games.

Mission 1:

Mission 2:

Mission 3:

2. Draw some of the objects of marine litter you encountered in the games.

Mission 1:

Mission 2:

Mission 3:

3. What is the origin of the marine litter you encountered?

Mission 1:

Mission 2:

Mission 3:

4. Explain how these objects can end up in the ocean.

Mission 1:

Mission 2:

Mission 3:

5. What are the consequences of this kind of litter in the ocean for marine life?

6. Describe 3 solutions to prevent, eliminate or reduce marine litter in the marine environment (oceans, beaches and coastlines).

